

I believe that science is collaborative and cumulative, and is better when it includes diverse people with diverse backgrounds. However, more than just the positive benefits for research productivity, there is a moral obligation for higher education, academia, and STEM to be inclusive and accessible to all members of society. Within and adjacent to the academic community, individuals and groups are the victims of both historical and ongoing discrimination. Although there are many facets of the world that are outside of my direct control, I feel that it is important to use the power and privilege that I do have, to change and improve equitability in the spaces within which I live and work.

In my own career path, I have worked hard for my achievements, and have also benefitted from many privileges. I am a man, a US citizen and a native English speaker, and have had numerous educational advantages, such as programming classes in middle school. Consequently, I have not always easily empathized with the struggles faced by others. For example, when I first led tutorial sessions for the UCSD/SIO R Users Group, I often demonstrated code too quickly, not realizing that concepts that are intuitive for me now are actually the result of substantial practice over many years and thus are not always accessible for new programmers. This experience has motivated me to be more mindful of my "expert blindness" and recognize that my colleagues and students have unique experiences and face different barriers. To help address this cognitive bias more directly, I now use the exercise of creating user personas when preparing to teach or communicate in formal settings. This practice helps me to identify my core message and how to best reach diverse audiences.

More broadly speaking, I recognize that there are a multitude of practices within academia that place undue burdens on people. Although some of these practices are viewed as "tradition", they may inadvertently act as gatekeeping mechanisms that prevent academic spaces from being as inclusive and accessible as they could be. For example, "happy hour" social functions at conferences or departments are often held in the evenings and in the presence of beer or wine. Such events can exclude those who have childcare or other dependent care responsibilities, are otherwise unavailable outside of typical work hours, or are uncomfortable due to the presence of alcohol. To be clear, such events are rarely intended maliciously, and colleagues socializing with alcohol after hours is a perfectly acceptable activity. Rather, conscious effort is needed to make academic spaces more explicitly welcoming, instead of reinforcing existing power structures and privileges.

My thinking on the subject of societal equity and justice has changed over time, as a result of both explicit training (e.g. in inclusive pedagogy, ally skills, and bystander intervention), and self-education. I expect that how I think about this topic, how I communicate and teach it, and my actions will continue to evolve as I learn about issues and work towards solutions. Below are some examples of my past and current work:

- From 2010-2012, I volunteered as a tutor for students at the City Heights Public Library. Many of these students came from a local elementary-school and were English-language learners identified by the school's social workers as needing academic help.
- When invited to give talks or participate in symposia, I ask my inviter whether different dimensions of diversity (e.g. gender, race, career stage) have been taken into consideration. This has sometimes resulted in my turning down opportunities and instead recommending others who could go in my place. Similarly, when assigning reviewers as an editor, I strive to assemble a set of reviewers that span gender, career stage, and geographical location using both the journal's database and the diversifyEEB list.

- Codes of Conduct are statements of the behavioral norms within a community and how violations of those norms will be addressed. In several of my communities, I have helped to craft such guidelines, and ensure that the codes of conduct are visible and communicated to attendees at events. As an example, the code of conduct for the UF Carpentries Club can be found at <https://www.uf-carpentries.org/code-of-conduct/>.
- I work to create mentoring and career training opportunities for students. For example, last summer I organized sessions for lab members to practice their talks and give each other feedback. I have also led the organization of two Research Bazaar events for Gainesville, which have included career panels, diversity and inclusion talks and discussion panels, and networking opportunities (see <https://resbaz.github.io/resbaz2019/gainesville/> for the 2019 event website).
- I educate myself about issues related to inclusion in society and academia through self-directed readings, and voluntary workshops. I attended an ally ship workshop at the 2017 annual meeting of the American Fisheries Society and a bystander intervention workshop at the 2018 annual meeting of the Ecological Society of America.
- I am on the leadership of the Gainesville Ally Skills Network, which educates individuals on how they can use their privilege to counteract systems of oppression in everyday situations. I and others were trained through a "Train-the-Trainers" event taught by Frame Shift Consulting (<https://frameshiftconsulting.com/ally-skills-workshop/>) to lead our own workshops—on October 14, we taught such a workshop to graduate students, postdocs, and staff. Importantly, these workshops focus on practical actions, so that the burden of addressing issues around inclusion and equity do not depend on labor from underrepresented and oppressed groups.

Mentoring Philosophy

My fundamental rule is to acknowledge the humanity of others. To me, this means approaching situations with empathy for people. In my role as the leader of a research group, I would work towards developing (and iterating) a training plan that gives trainees flexibility in attaining the skills for future career goals. An important first step in this process is to identify the personal values of each trainee; because no one has the full picture of all possible career paths or useful skills, this helps trainees establish the agency to make the best decisions for themselves, rather than be limited by the imagination or networks of their mentors.

Moreover, I believe that reflecting on one's values can help to drive motivation for skill attainment. In the absence of this linkage, it can be easy to mistake metrics of research outputs (e.g. papers, grants, data and software) as measures of one's worth. Instead, I hope to encourage the mindset that these metrics are merely markers (and lagging, too) of effort and personal development; while useful for external validation, they are not goals in and of themselves. Thus, I aim to help trainees achieve success based on what they determine to be most meaningful, by providing a supportive and encouraging environment for them to experiment, learn from mistakes, and find (or build) their next career stage.